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Study of Psychosomatic Disorders with Reference to Ayurveda Classical Texts

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ABSTRACT

Psychosomatic disorders term derived from psyche (mind), soma (body) and disorders (disturbance in health). Collectively it can be known as physical disease that can be caused or made worse by psychological factors. With reference to Ayurveda, literature found on manodaihika vyadhi but they were not described in Ayurveda classical texts under this category. So, this study could be based on finding the hidden knowledge about psychosomatic disorders as per in Ayurveda classical texts. The Charaka Samhita, Sushruta Samhita, Ashtangahradaya Samhita, Madhawa Nidana, and earlier research from electronic sources like PubMed and Google Scholar were cited in the study. After the study it seems that there is no separate chapter for manodaihika vyadhi but in chapters where the authors discussed different diseases, they mentioned about psychosomatic disorders when referring nidana. These disorders can be categorized as direct psychosomatic disorders, psychotic disorders which having psychosomatic nature, dosha predominant disorders which having causative factors of manasika bhava and diseases which having influence of manasika bhava to manifest diseases.

Keywords: *Ayurveda, psychosomatic disorders, manodaihika vyadhi*

INTRODUCTION

History of psychosomatic disorders as old as the establishment of human civilization [20] because mind and body cannot be split up as separate entities as they are having inter relationship. Over three thousand years ago in which time

Ayurveda was originated in India classical texts Caraka Samhita (6th century B.C.), Sushruta Samhita (6th century B.C.), Ashtangahradaya Samhita (2nd century A.D.), Madhava Nidana (8th century A.D.) (Narayanaswamy,1981) weredescribed about psychosomatic disorders from their

original terminology Manodaihika Vyadhi[20]. Locution psychosomatic derived from the Greek word's "psyche" and "soma." The root "Psyche" which indicates mind and "soma" which signifies body.[11] can be collectively stated as relationship of mind and body. The word disorder can be explained as disturbance of homeostasis; many aspects of the systems are affected. In this study focus was given to psychosomatic disorders which also can be indicated as "a physical disease that thought to be caused or made worse by internal factors"[20]. This study based on psychosomatic disorders with reference to Ayurveda classical texts due to lack of knowledge about those disorders and to collate concealed knowledge of psychosomatic disorders in Ayurveda classical texts.

METHODOLOGY

As this subject, psychosomatic disorders touch vast area those disorders were not indicate as a discrete chapter named as Manodaihika Vyadhi in Ayurveda classical texts, yet they were described under several chapters which include roga. Primary data collection was encompassed with Caraka Samhita, Sushruta Samhita and Ashtangahridaya Samhita which categorized under vrddhatrayi and Madhava Nidana under laghutrayi. Secondary data was evoked from previous studies which gathered through electronic databases including PubMed and Google Scholar. Secondary data were congregated only including published articles, unpublished articles were excluded. Only English language articles were selected. Searching terms were included Ayurveda, psychosomatic disorders, manodaihika vyadhi, history, prevalence.

RESULTS

Altered functions of mind which are dhee, dhriti and smrti gives rise to psychosomatic disorders as well as somatic and psychic disorders.

Considering about aetiology of psychosomatic disorders manasika guna namely sattva, rajas and tamas[5,23] and manasikabhavas cannot be neglected. Manasikabhavas can be disclosed as kama (lustre), krodha (anger), lobha (greed), moha (delusion), irshya (jealousy), maana (pride), mada (neurosis), soka (grief), chinta (depression), udvega (anxiety), bhaya (fear) and harsha (euphoria)[5] all above mentioned are aetiology for psychosomatic disorders. Hence stressful object interacts with sattva (mind) and process imbalance of rajas and tamas mano doshas. When manasa doshas are exceeded the limit of stress sharirika dosha viz vata, pitta and kapha were started to manifest bodily diseases which can be further elaborated as psychosomatic disorders. If indriya buddhi having tendency to aggravate rajas in mind, it will result to aggravate sharirika dosha i.e. pitta and vata. If this situation reversed tamas is increased in mind and vitiation of kapha resulted [20,21,22]. This sequence can be pointed out as follows.

- Temporary physical changes related to acute emotional states
- Somatic reactions expressing an inner conflict with symbolic form
- Tissue changes and organic disease resulting in part from long standing emotional problems[21].

In accordance with acharya Sushruta's concept of shat kriya kala phases of developing psychosomatic disorders can be described just like that,

- Psychic phase – Sanchaya
- Psychoneurotic phase – Prakopa and Prasara
- Psychosomatic phase – Sthanasamsraya & Vyakti
- Advanced organic phase – Bheda [22]

Categorization of psychosomatic disorders can be carried out into two parts with the firstly involved cause is

- Psychosomatic disorders where manas involved in the beginning and
 - Manovikara where sharira involved first and later manas is involved[23].
- Another classification can be stated in accordance with manasikabhava such asnkrodha janya and shoka janya

Table 1: Summarizing of disorders which having psychosomatic origin with reference to classical Ayurveda texts.

Classical Ayurveda Text List of Disorders Having Psychosomatic Origin

Classical Ayurveda Text	List of Disorders Having Psychosomatic Origin
<i>Caraka Samhita</i>	<i>Shiro roga (vataja shiro roga), hrd roga (vataja, pittaja & kaphaja), madhumeha, ojas kshaya, unmada, apasmara, mruta garbha, abhinyasaja jwara (kama, shoka, bhaya & krodhaja jwara), vataja gulma, kushta, dhatukshyajanita yakshma, pandu roga, pittaja kasa, kshayaja kasa, bhayaja atisara, shokaja atisara, vataja chardi, trishna, vrana, arochaka, urusthambha, vatarakta, shukra dosha, bhijopaghataka klaivya, kshayaja klaivya, ashta sthanya roga, tandra, anantavata</i>
<i>Sushruta Samhita</i>	<i>Ojas kshaya, karshya, manasa klaivya, netra roga, grahaavesha, jwara (kamaja, shokaja, bhayaja & krodhaja), shokaja atisara, raktapitta, murccha, panathya, trishna, chardi, arochaka, apasmara, unmada</i>
<i>Ashtangahrdaya Samhita</i>	<i>Abhishangaja jwara (krodhaja jwara, bhayaja jwara, shokaja jwara, kamaja jwara), rajayakshma, arochaka, atisara (bhayaja & shokaja), vidradhi, unmada (aadija (manasa) unmada), apasmara</i>
<i>Madhawa Nidana</i>	<i>Jwara (kamaja, bhayaja & shokaja), shokaja atisara, ajirna, raktapitta, rajayakshma, shoka shosha, kshayaja kasa, agantuka arochaka, chardi, trishna, murccha, bhrama, unmada (shokadi manobhavaja unmada),</i>

Table 2: Disorders having psychosomatic influence as per the classical Ayurveda texts.

Disorder	As per Charaka Samhita	As per Sushruta Samhita	As per Ashtangahrdaya Samhita	As per Madhava Nidana
<i>Jwara</i>	<i>Abhinyasaja jwara (Kamaja jwara, Shokaja jwara, Bhayaja jwara, Krodhaja jwara)</i>	<i>Kamaja jwara Shokaja jwara Bhayaja jwara Krodhaja jwara</i>	<i>Abhishangaja jwara (Krodhaja jwara, Bhayaja jwara, Shokaja jwara, Kamaja jwara)</i>	<i>Kamaja jwara Bhayaja jwara Shokaja jwara</i>
<i>Atisara</i>	<i>Shokaja atisara Bhayaja atisara</i>	<i>Shokaja atisara</i>	Not Mentioned	<i>Shokaja atisara</i>
<i>Arshas</i>	<i>Vataja arshas Pittaja arshas Kaphaja arshas</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned
<i>Ajirna</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	<i>Ajirna</i>
<i>Krimi</i>	<i>Raktaja krimi</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned

<i>Pandu</i>	<i>Pandu</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned
<i>Raktapitta</i>	Not Mentioned	<i>Raktapitta</i>	Not Mentioned	<i>Raktapitta</i>
<i>Rajayakshma</i>	<i>Dhatukshayajanitha yakshma</i>	Not Mentioned	<i>Rajayakshma</i>	<i>Rajayakshma</i>
<i>Shosha</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	<i>Shoka shosha</i>
<i>Kasa</i>	<i>Pittaja kasa Kshayaja kasa</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	<i>Kshayaja kasa</i>
<i>Arochaka</i>	<i>Arochaka</i>	<i>Arochaka</i>	<i>Arochaka</i>	<i>Aganthuka arochaka</i>
<i>Chardi</i>	<i>Vataja chardi Dvishtarthayog aja chardi</i>	<i>Chardi</i>	Not Mentioned	<i>Chardi</i>
<i>Trishna</i>	<i>Trishna</i>	<i>Trishna</i>	Not Mentioned	<i>Trishna</i>
<i>Murcha</i>	Not Mentioned	<i>Murcha</i>	Not Mentioned	<i>Murcha</i>
<i>Tandra</i>	<i>Tandra</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned
<i>Bhrama</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	<i>Bhrama</i>
<i>Sanyasa</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	<i>Sanyasa</i>
<i>Paanaathya</i>	<i>Vataja madathya Pittaja madathya</i>	<i>Paanathya</i>	Not Mentioned	<i>Madya vikara</i>
<i>Unmada</i>	<i>Unmada</i>	<i>Unmada</i>	<i>Aadija (manasa) unmada</i>	<i>Shokadi manobhavaja unmada</i>

<i>Apasmara</i>	<i>Apasmara</i>	<i>Apasmara</i>	<i>Apasmara</i>	<i>Apasmara</i>
<i>Urusthambha</i>	<i>Urusthambha</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned
<i>Vatarakta</i>	<i>Vatarakta</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned
<i>Vrikka Shula</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	<i>Vrikka shula</i>
<i>Gulma</i>	<i>Vataja gulma</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned

<i>Hrd Roga</i>	<i>Vataja hrd Roga Pittaja hrd roga Kaphaja hrd roga</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	<i>Hrd roga</i>
<i>Madhume ha</i>	<i>Madhumeha Vataja prameha Pittaja prameha</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned
<i>Medovrid dhi</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	<i>Medo vrid dhi</i>
<i>Udara</i>	<i>Udara</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned
<i>Vidradhi</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	<i>Vidradhi</i>	Not Mentioned
<i>Vrana</i>	<i>Vrana</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned
<i>Kushta</i>	<i>Kushta</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	<i>Kushta</i>
<i>Shvitra</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	<i>Shvitra</i>
<i>Palitha</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	<i>Palitha</i>
<i>Vyanga</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	<i>Vyanga</i>
<i>Prathishy a</i>	<i>Pinasa</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned
<i>Netra Roga</i>	Not Mentioned	Netra roga	Not Mentioned	<i>Netra roga</i>
<i>Shiro Roga</i>	<i>Vataja Shiro Roga Anantavata</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	<i>Pittaja shiro roga</i>
<i>Asrugdar a</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	<i>Asrugdara</i>
<i>Yonikand a</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	<i>Yonikanda</i>
<i>Mruthaga</i>	<i>Mruthagarbha</i>	Not	Not Mentioned	Not

<i>rbha</i>		Mentioned		Mentioned
<i>Garbhapatha</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	<i>Garbhapata</i>
<i>Sutika Roga</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	<i>Sutika roga</i>
<i>Sthanya Roga</i>	<i>Ashta shanya roga</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned
<i>Grahavesha</i>	Not Mentioned	Grahavesha	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned
<i>Shukra Dosh</i>	<i>Shukra dosha</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned
<i>Klaivya</i>	<i>Bhijopaghataka klaivya Kshayaja klaivya</i>	<i>Manasa klaivya</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned
<i>Karshya</i>	Not Mentioned	<i>Karshya</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned
<i>Ojas Kshaya</i>	<i>Ojas kshaya</i>	<i>Ojas kshaya</i>	Not Mentioned	Not Mentioned

Table 3: Number of psychosomatic disorders discussed in Ayurveda classical texts.

Name of Ayurveda classical texts	Number of psychosomatic disorders discussed
Charaka Samhita	43
Sushruta Samhita	18
Ashtangahrada Samhita	11
Madhava Nidana	31

Table 4: Causative factor of Each Psychosomatic Disorders with Reference to Ayurveda Classical Texts.

Disorder	As per Charaka Samhita	As per Sushruta Samhita	As per Ashtangahrada Samhita	As per Madhava Nidana
<i>Jwara</i>	<i>Kamaja jwara – Kama Shokaja jwara – shoka Bhayaja jwara - bhaya Krodhaja jwara – krodha</i>	<i>Kamaja jwara - kama Shokaja jwara shoka Bhayaja jwara - bhaya Krodhaja jwara – krodha</i>	<i>Krodhaja jwara - krodha Bhayaja jwara - bhaya Shokaja jwara – shoka Kamaja</i>	<i>Kamaja jwara – chitta vibhramsha due to kama Bhaya ja jwara - bhaya Shok</i>

			<i>jwara - kama</i>	<i>aja jwara – shoka</i>
<i>Atisara</i>	<i>Shokaja atisara - shoka Bhayaja atisara – bhaya</i>	<i>Shokaja atisara - shoka</i>	–	<i>Shokaja atisara – shoka</i>
<i>Arshas</i>	<i>Vataja arshas – shoka Pittaja arshas – krodha Kaphaja arshas – free of thoughts</i>	–	–	–
<i>Ajirna</i>	–	–	–	<i>Irshaya, Bhaya, Chinta, Shoka</i>
<i>Krimi</i>	<i>Raktaja krimi - Santhapa (excessive worrying)</i>	–	–	–
<i>Pandu</i>	<i>Kama, Bhaya, Krodha, Shoka</i>	–	–	–
<i>Raktapitta</i>	–	<i>Krodha, Shoka, Bhaya</i>	–	<i>Shoka</i>
<i>Rajayakshma</i>	<i>Irshya, Eargeness, Bhaya, Shoka, Krodha</i>	–	<i>Krodha, Shoka</i>	<i>Irshya, Vishaada</i>
<i>Shosha</i>	–	–	–	<i>Shoka</i>
<i>Kasa</i>	<i>Pittaja kasa – Krodha Kshayaja kasa – Shoka</i>	–	–	<i>Kshayaja kasa – Worrying, Shoka</i>
<i>Arochaka</i>	<i>Shoka, Bhaya, Atilobha, Atikrodha</i>	<i>Kama, Shoka, Bhaya</i>	<i>Shoka, Bhaya, Lobha, Kama, Krodha, Irshya</i>	<i>Shoka, Bhaya, Atilobha, Krodha</i>
<i>Chardi</i>	<i>Vataja chardi – Shoka, Bhaya Dvishtarthayog aja chardi – manasthapa due to sight of incompatible foods & drinks</i>	<i>Bhaya, Udvega</i>	–	<i>Bhaya, Udvega</i>
<i>Trishna</i>	<i>Bhaya, Shoka, Krodha</i>	<i>Shoka</i>	–	<i>Bhaya, Krodha</i>
<i>Murcha</i>	–	<i>Alpa sattva guna</i>	–	<i>Alpa sattva guna</i>
<i>Tandra</i>	<i>Shoka</i>	–	–	–
<i>Bhrama</i>	–	–	–	<i>Rajo guna</i>
<i>Sanyasa</i>	–	–	–	<i>Tamas guna</i>
<i>Paanaathya</i>	<i>Vataja madathya –</i>	<i>Krodha, Bhaya,</i>	–	<i>Madya</i>

	<i>shoka Pittaja madathya – krodha</i>	<i>Shoka</i>		<i>vikara – krodha, bhaya, shoka</i>
<i>Unmada</i>	Worrying (<i>manasthapa</i>), <i>Kama</i> , <i>Anuraga</i> , <i>Krodha</i> , <i>Lobha</i> , <i>Harsha</i> , <i>Bhaya</i> , <i>Moha</i> , <i>Parishrama</i> , <i>Shoka</i> , <i>Chinta</i> , <i>Udvega</i> , Excessive mental trauma	<i>Shokaja unmada - shoka</i>	<i>Aadija (manasa) unmada – shoka</i> Other types – <i>Manasika dosha</i>	<i>Shokadi manobhavaj a unmada – Athishoka, atiyoga of Bhaya, Shoka, Kama, Harsha</i>
<i>Apasmara</i>	<i>Rajas & Tamas guna, Kama, Krodha, Lobha, Moha, Harsha,</i>	<i>Rajas, Tamas</i>	<i>Chinta, Shoka, Bhaya,</i> diminution of	<i>Chinta, Shoka</i>
	<i>Bhaya, Shoka, Chinta, Udvega</i>		<i>Buddhi & Sattvaguna</i>	
<i>Urusthambha</i>	<i>Bhaya</i>	–	–	–
<i>Vatarakta</i>	<i>Krodha</i>	–	–	–
<i>Vrikka Shula</i>	Not Mentioned	–	–	<i>Shoka</i>
<i>Gulma</i>	<i>Vataja gulma – Shoka</i>	–	–	–
<i>Hrd Roga</i>	<i>Vataja hrd Roga - Shoka Pittaja hrd roga - Krodha Kaphaja hrd roga – Free of worry</i>	–	–	<i>Chinta</i>
<i>Prameha</i>	<i>Madhumeha - Avoidance of thinking / worry Pittaja prameha – krodha Vataja prameha – shoka</i>	–	–	–
<i>Medovridhi</i>	–	–	–	<i>Mada</i>
<i>Udara</i>	<i>Mano abhighata</i>	–	–	–
<i>Vidradhi</i>	–	–	<i>Viruddha cheshta</i>	–
<i>Vrana</i>	<i>Shoka, Krodha</i>	–	–	–
<i>Kushta</i>	<i>Santhapa (excessive worrying)</i>	–	–	<i>Bhaya</i>
<i>Shvitra</i>	–	–	–	<i>Bhaya</i>
<i>Palitha</i>	–	–	–	<i>Krodha,</i>

				<i>Shoka</i>
<i>Vyanga</i>	–	–	–	<i>Krodha</i>
<i>Prathishya</i>	<i>Peenasa – krodha</i>	–	–	–
<i>Netra Roga</i>	–	<i>Krodha, Shoka</i>	–	<i>Krodha, Shoka</i>
<i>Shiro Roga</i>	<i>Vataja Shiro Roga – Shoka, Bhaya Anantavata – Atishoka</i> All types of shiro roga – <i>Manasthapa</i>	–	–	<i>Pittaja shiro roga – Krodha</i>
<i>Asrugdara</i>	–	–	–	<i>Shoka</i>
<i>Yonikanda</i>	–	–	–	<i>Atikrodha</i>
<i>Mruthagarbha</i>	<i>Krodha, Shoka, Irshya, Bhaya, Traasa</i>	–	–	–
<i>Garbhapatna</i>	–	–	–	Exhausted <i>manasika dosha</i>
<i>Sutika Roga</i>	–	–	–	Exhausted <i>manasika dosha</i>
<i>Sthanya Roga</i>	Exhausted mind	–	–	–
<i>Grahavesha</i>		<i>Bhaya, Harsha</i>	–	–
<i>Shukra Dosha</i>	<i>Bhaya, Krodha</i>		–	–
<i>Klaivya</i>	<i>Bhijopaghataka klaivya – Chinta, Shoka, Bhaya Kshayaja klaivya – Chinta, Shoka, Bhaya, Krodha</i>	<i>Manasa klaivya – Manasa aghata</i>	–	–
<i>Karshya</i>	–	<i>Athishoka, Athibhaya, excessive thought</i>	–	–
<i>Ojas Kshaya</i>	Worrying, <i>Shoka, Bhutopaghata</i> (Major mental illness)	<i>Krodha, Shoka, Chinta</i>	–	–

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Just as above table *manasika dosha* namely *rajas* and *tamas* combining with other *manasikabhavas*, psychosomatic diseases are manifested. Not only that diminution of *sattva guna* also caused to above diseases. *Kama, shoka, bhaya,*

krodha, chitta vibhramsha, irshya, chinta, vishaada, lobha, udvega, raaga, harsha, moha, mada and *traasa* are the *manasikabhavas* which responsible for the diseases above mentioned. Among these causative factors *Kama, Krodha, Shoka*

and *Bhaya* are the main psychic factors which affect to psychosomatic disorders.

Nourishing from above mentioned knowledge these diseases can be categorized as

- Direct psychosomatic disorders
- Psychic disorders which having psychosomatic nature
- Dosha predominant disorders which having causative factors of manasika bhava
- Diseases which are having influence of manasika bhava to manifest diseases

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